

A PHARMACEUTICAL STUDY ON GANDHAMRUTHA RASA

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ABSTRACT

Rasa Shastra is an important branch of *Ayurveda* which deals with the use of metallic and mineral drugs which are pharmaceutically processed and rendered fit for internal administration. These are known as *Rasa Oushadis*. The word *Rasa Shastra* literally means the "science of mercury". Knowledge of *Rasa* has been in existence from the time immemorial. Exploration of natural resources for the benefit of human beings is the object of this therapy. Medieval period can be treated as a golden age for the development of this science. It is recognized as a medical science with an independent philosophical background in 14th century. *Rasa Oushadis* have faster action in smaller doses, quicker assimilation, excellent therapeutic values, longer shelf life.^[1] The present study is concerned with the immunomodulatory action of one among the herbo-mineral preparation called *Gandhamrutha*

Rasa,^[2] explained in the classical text *Bhaishajya Ratnavali*, which has indication of eradication of *Jara* and *Akala Mrityu*.^[3] It contains *Rasa Sindura*, *Shudha Gandhaka* and *Ghrutha Kumari*.^[4] *Rasa Sindura* is a herbo-mineral preparation containing *Shudha Parada*, *Shudha Gandhaka* and *Vatankura Swarasa*.^[5] *Rasa Sindura* comes under *Kupipakwa Rasayana*^[6] mentioned in *Rasa Tarangini*. *Shudha Parada* is being extracted from *Hingulotha Parada*,^[7] mentioned in *Rasa Tarangini*, which has properties similar to *Ashta*

Samskrita Parada.^[8] *Shudha Gandhaka* is obtained through *Kurma Puta* method mentioned in *Ayurveda Prakasha*^[9] Till now no study has been conducted on *Gandhamrutha Rasa*, so this study aims to prepare *Gandhamrutha Rasa*.

KEYWORDS: *Gandhamrutha Rasa*, *Rasa Sindura*, *Hingulotha Parada*.

INTRODUCTION

Gandhamrutha Rasa is a traditional Ayurvedic herbal-mineral formulation mentioned in the *Vajikarana Adhyaya* of *Bhaisajya Ratnavali*. Despite its traditional use, no scientific study has been conducted on this formulation. This study aimed to evaluate the pharmaceutical, analytical, and immunomodulatory properties of *Gandhamrutha Rasa*.

METHODS

The study involved the preparation of *Gandhamrutha Rasa* using traditional Ayurvedic methods. The Pharmaceutical production of *Rasa Sindura* and the formulation was prepared with *Rasa Sindura* and *Gandhaka*, using *Gritha Kumari Swarasa* as the *Bhavana Dravya*.

METHODOLOGY

The present study involved the preparation and purification of various Ayurvedic substances, including *Gandhaka*, *Hingula*, *Parada*, *Rasa Sindura*, and *Gandhamrutha rasa*. The following procedures were employed:

Hingulotha Parada and *Gandhaka Shodhana*.

For *Rasa Sindura* preparation, *Kacha Kupi* method.^[10]

Rasa Sindura and *Shudha Gandhaka* is made into *Kajjali*.^[11]

Then it is subjected to *Bhavana*^[12] with *Ghrutha Kumari Swarasa*.

Subjected to *Laghuputa*^[13] after making it into *Chakrika* and *Bhasma* is obtained.^[14]

Gandhaka Shodhana Kurmaputa

Gandhaka (500g) was powdered and spread over a cloth tied around the mouth of a mud vessel containing 1 liter of milk. The vessel was sealed with another mud vessel using seven layers of *Sandhibandhana* and heated for a specified period.

Hingula Shodhana

Hingula (300g) was powdered and subjected to a 24-hour grinding process (*Mardana*) with lemon juice. The resulting powder was shaped into uniform tablets (*Chakrikas*).

AHingulotha Parada

Purified *Hingula* (323g) was placed in a lower pot, sealed with another pot using seven layers of *Sandhibandhana*, and heated for a specified period. The adhered *Parada* was scraped off, filtered, and collected.

Hingulotha Parada Shodhana

Purified *Parada* (104g) underwent trituration with *Haridra Churna* (6.32g), *Saindhava* (6.32g), and *Nimbu Swarasa* for 48 hours.

Kajjali Nirmana

Shudha Parada (91g) and *Shudha Gandhaka* (91g) were combined and subjected to rigorous grinding and mixing (*Mardana*) until a uniform jet black color was attained.

Kajjali Bhavana with Vatankura Swarasa

Kajjali (165g) underwent *Mardana* with *Vatankura Swarasa* (40ml) for 3.5 hours.

Rasa Sindura Preparation

Bhavita Kajjali (160g) was filled into a *Kacakupi*, sealed, and heated for a specified period. The resulting *Rasa Sindura* was collected, triturated, and stored.

Bhavana of Rasa Sindura and Shudha Gandhaka with Kumari Swarasa

Rasa Sindura (66g) and *Shudha Gandhaka* (132g) underwent *Mardana* with *Kumari Swarasa* (70ml) for 4 hours.

Chakrikarana for Laghu Puta

The *Bhavita* mixture was rolled and compressed into uniform *Chakrikas*.

Laghu Puta

The *Chakrikas* were arranged in a *sarava*, sealed, and heated for a specified period. The resulting *Gandhamrutha Bhasma* was collected and preserved.

These procedures were performed with utmost care and attention to detail to ensure the quality and efficacy of the prepared substances.

RESULTS AND OBSERVATIONS

1. *Gandhaka shodhana*

The purified *Gandhaka*, now in granular form, had settled at the bottom of the lower vessel, mingling with the milk. This *Shudha Gandhaka* was collected, thoroughly washed, dried, and stored for future use.

Table 1: Showing temperature of *gandhaka shodhana*.

Time	Temperature in degree celcius
1:30 pm	37.3
1:40 pm	83.5
1:55 pm	275
2:05 pm	286
2:15 pm	255
2:25 pm	196
2:35 pm	155
2:45 pm	146
3:00 pm	110.2
3:15 pm	70.5
3:25 pm	53.8
3:35 pm	47
3:45 pm	45.1
3:55 pm	43
4:05 pm	40
4:15 pm	38

Table 2: showing results of *gandhaka shodhana*.

<i>Ashudha gandhaka</i>	Milk	<i>Vanopala</i>	<i>Shudha gandhaka</i> obtained	Loss %
500 g	1 litre	1916 gm	489 gm	2.2

2. *Hingula shodhana*

Colour of *hingula* changed from a deep red to a brick red when *nimbu swarasam* was added. After the *nimbu swarasam* was dried off, *swarasam* was added in frequent intervals.

Table 3: Showing results of *hingula shodhana*.

Name of the sample	Wt before <i>shodhana</i>	Wt after <i>shodhana</i>	Amount of <i>nimbu swarasam</i>	Colour at the end of <i>shodhana</i>
<i>Ashudha hingula</i>	300 gm	323 gm	90 ml	Brick red

3. *Hingulotha parada*

During *urdhwa patana*, a characteristic smell was felt during the procedure.

Wide range of temperature difference was noted between the lower pot and upper pot.

During collection, *parada* appeared as grey coloured ash inside the upper pot.

Table 4: showing results of *hingulotha parada*.

Wt of hingula	Wt of obtained <i>parada</i>	% of loss	Colour	Appearance of <i>parada</i>
302 gm	104 gm	75%	Silver white	Liquid, shining

4. *Hingulotha parada shodhana*

After few hours of trituration, colour of *haridra* changed to green gram colour.

Parada started to disintergrate within ½ hours of trituration.

Till the addition of *nimbu swarasa*, disintegration was not complete and some amount of *parada* remained as large globule.

After the addition of *nimbu swarasa*, *parada* has remained as fine globules till the completion of *mardana*.

Table 5: Showing results of *hingulotha parada shodhana*.

Wt of <i>parada</i> before <i>shodhana</i>	Wt of <i>parada</i> after <i>shodhana</i>	% of loss	Colour	Appearance
104 gm	91 gm	12 %	Silver white	Liquid and shining

6. *Kajjali nirmana*

Table 6: showing observations of *kajjali*.

Features	Time
<i>Parada</i> turned into fine globules	5 minutes
Colour of the mixture changed to light greyish yellow	20 minutes
Mixture turned to grey colour	45 minutes
Globules of <i>parada</i> completely disappeared	1 hour
Colour of mixture turned to blackish grey	4 hours
Mixture turned to black colour	7 ½ hours
<i>Rekhapoornatvam</i>	10 hours
<i>Varitaratvam</i>	11 hours
<i>Nischandratvam</i>	95 hours

Table 7: showing results of *kajjali*.

Initial weight	Obtained weight	Loss %	Colour	Consistency
182 gm	165 gm	9.3	<i>Kajjalabha</i>	Fine powder

7. *Kajjali bhavana with vatankura swarasa*

Mardana was started after adding *swarasa*, till the *kajjali* was soaked.

After 5 minutes, *kajjali* was completely mixed with *swarasa* with a liquid consistency.

Mardana was smooth without friction, as liquid content was high.

After 45 minutes, on continuous *mardana*, the liquid content was observed to be reduced.

After 2 hours, the mixture was observed to be thicker and on *mardana* slight friction was observed.

After 3 hours 20 minutes, the *bhavita lakshanas* were observed and the *bhavana* was stopped and was kept for drying.

Table 8: showing results of *kajjali mardana* with *vatankura swarasa*.

<i>Kajjali</i> taken	<i>Swarasa</i> taken	<i>Kajjali</i> before drying	<i>Kajjali</i> after drying	Loss %
165 gm	40 ml	182 gm	160 gm	4

8. Rasa sindura

Table 9: showing observation of *rasa sindura*.

Parameters	Time
Slight white fumes	1 hour 30 minutes
Dense white fumes	3 hours
Characteristic smell of <i>gandhaka</i>	4 hours 30 minutes
Yellow fumes	5 hours
<i>Sheeta shalaka sanchalana</i> (<i>kajjali</i> started to melt) <i>madhyamagni</i> initiated	5 hours and 30 minutes
<i>Tatpta shalaka sanchalana</i> (blue flame observed)	10 hours and 30 minutes
Blue flame observed	18 hours and 30 minutes
Blue flame was diminished	21 hours
Corking done (<i>teevraagni</i> initiated)	22 hours
Fire lit off	25 hours

Table 10: showing results of *rasa sindura*.

<i>Kajjali</i> used	Fuel	Time	Obtained <i>Rasa sindura</i>	Yield %
160 gm	35 kg	25 hours	66 gm	41.25 gm

9. Bhavana of *rasa sindura* and *gandhaka* with *kumari swarasa*

After 3 minutes of *mardana*, whole mixture was soaked in the *swarasa*.

Mardana was smooth, water like consistency.

After 45 minutes, consistency of loose paste.

After 1 hour 30 minutes, the mixture turned to a cream like consistency.

After 3 hours, stickiness reduced but not able to make *varti* (*bhavita lakshana* not attained).

After 4 hours and 30 minutes, the mixture was able to be rolled into *varti* and smooth (*bhavita lakshana* attained).

Table 11: showing results of mardana of *rasa sindura* and *gandhaka* with *kumari swarasa*.

Weight after <i>bhavana</i>	Gain	Gain %
240 gm	42 gm	17.5

10. *Chakrikarana* for *laghuputa*

Table 12: showing results of *chakrikarana* for *laghu puta*.

Total <i>chakrikas</i>	Weight before drying	Weight after Drying	Total weight	Loss %
62	4 gm	3.5 gm	218 gm	10

11. *Laghuputa* (*Gandhamarutha rasa* preparation)

After cooling, the *sarava* was carefully opened by removing the sealing *Multani mitti*. The contents were then revealed, yielding *Gandhamarutha Rasa* in the form of a grey-colored ash. This transformative process, facilitated by controlled heat and atmospheric conditions, had successfully converted the *Chakrikas* into a potent, bioavailable *Bhasma*. The resulting grey ash was carefully collected and preserved for future therapeutic applications; its efficacy enhanced by the rigorous preparation process.

Table 13: showing results of *laghu puta*.

	Total <i>Chakrikas</i>	Total weight	Total <i>vanopalas</i>	Weight of <i>vanopalas</i>	Obtained <i>Bhasma</i>	Obtained %
Sample A	17	59 gm	8	1197 gm	13 gm	22%
Sample B	17	59 gm	8	983 gm	12 gm	20%
Sample C	16	56 gm	8	968 gm	14 gm	24%

DISCUSSION

The study demonstrates the pharmaceutical processing of *Gandhamrutha Rasa*, explained as a *rasayana* in Ayurvedic medicine with the practical aspects of the steps involved in it.

CONCLUSION

According to conceptual study, *Gandhamrutha rasa* possesses *prabhava* due to its materialist combination during pharmaceutical processing. *Prabhava* remains the highest in hierarchy of pharmacological action of a drug. As *rasadravyas* find its utility in *asadhya rogas*, *Gandhamrutha rasa* has the potential to cure *akalamrityu*.

Pharmaceutically *Gandamrutha rasa* can be prepared from commonly available ingredients- *parada, gandhaka, ghrutha kumari*. It is a *bhasma* and the process involved here makes the medicine potent. *Hingulotha Parada* is done by the method mentioned in *Rasa Tarangini* and *gandhaka sodhana* by *kurmaputa* method. The *rasa sindura* is made as *kupipakva rasayana* for the final product. The final process of *Gandhamrutha rasa* is the processing of *rasa sindura* and *shudha gandhaka* levigated with *ghritakumari swarasa* and subjected for *laghuputa* and the *Bhasma* is obtained. The medicine should be satisfied with the *pareekshas* like *varitaratwa, unnama, rekhapurnatwa, nischandratwa* etc.

Further research is necessary to fully elucidate the mechanisms underlying *Gandhamrutha Rasa's* immunomodulation and to explore its clinical applications.

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